

Information Technology and its role in the Performance of the Human Resource Management Function: As a study a selected firm in the City of Blantyre, Malawi

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Abstract

When new employees are being engaged, traditional the personnel function would require them to submit personal information, certificate copies, medical certificates National Identity cards, among others. These would be photocopied and filed within the human resources department or with the registry for future reference. The calculation of salaries and management of leave and other employee benefits would be done manually or on a single stand-alone computer, pay slips would be printed and the accountant will deposit pay cheques into the accounts of the employees at the bank.

For factory workers, clocking cards are no longer useful as employees can use biometric finger prints to clock in and out and the system records the precise time the employee clocked and out in a particular day.

This has nowadays stopped in many companies and even government departments with the coming of information technology and computerized payroll systems which would manage data, leave, third party payments and salaries, leaving very little paper work for filing if any. Information technology has changed the way human resource functions are carried out and this has also led to reduced operation costs, which means more profit for the organisation and also an organisation that would remain sustainable into the future.

Keywords: Payroll systems, HR Functions, IT, Employee benefits.

Introduction

The use of information technology has

improved human life in the workplace and the way of doing things in the personnel department. Using information technology has improved the way human resource management functions are carried out for example the administrative aspects such as employee benefits management, remuneration and compensation. Some activities as salaries and wages calculations and payments, third party payments such as medical aid, pension and provident fund deductions, leave management as well as training and development, not overlooking the whole process of recruitment, selection, placement and termination of employees have improved quite a lot. Information systems are also enabling human resource practitioners and management to carry out employee performance appraisals timely and effectively and management personnel records for quick retrieval and safe storage. The role of the HRM Department has also received recognition as a strategic function not a supporting one.

Literature Review

Human Resource Management (hrm)

This refers to the policies, practices and systems that influence employees' behaviour, attitudes and performance (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart and Wright, 2010:4). The responsibilities of human resource departments include, employment and recruitment, training and development, compensation, benefits, employment and community relations, personnel records, health and safety, and strategic planning (Noe et al, 2010:6). According to Noe et al (2010:5), only recently have companies looked at HRM

as a means of contributing to the profitability, quality and other business goals through enhancing and supporting business operations.

Changes In The Hrm Function Due Information Technology

According to Noe et al (2010:9) the amount of time that the HRM function devotes to administrative tasks is decreasing and its roles as a strategic business partner, change agent and employee advocate are increasing. The catalyst of the changes in many aspects has been information technology; Noe et al. (2010:9) cited administrative processes such as employee records and allowing employees to get information about and enroll in training, benefits and other programs. Outsourcing of administrative activities has also occurred, a situation where a third party or consultant, provides such services instead of the company itself (Noe et al 2010:9)

Role Of Information Technology In Human Resource Management

In their study Piry, Hatamkhibari, Janfeshan and Ghahramani (2013:1034) reiterated that in the present era implementation, development and maintenance of information systems for HRM is one of the most important business processes for managers and organisations as they are faced with new challenges. The Piry et al study (2013:1035) found that information technology produced some results in the practice of human resource management such as:

- The accuracy and speed of performance,
- Transparency and integrity in system design,
- Timely feedback,

- Development of staff skills,
- Conducting of necessary training through virtual education.

A study by Saha and Majumder (2017:82) defined performance appraisal is the process of assessing employee performance by way of comparing present performance with standards which have been already informed to employees, subsequently providing feedback to employees about their performance level for the purpose of improving their performance as needed by the organisation. Kettley and Reilly (2003) cited in Saha and Majumder (2017:84) defined a Computerized Human Resource Information System (CHRIS) as consisting of, “a fully integrated organisation wide network resource related data, information services, databases, tools and transactions.” In the same study Saha and Majumder, (2017:84) cited Chamaru de Alwis (2010) who defined Human Resource Information System (HRIS), as “a computerized system used to collect, record, store, analysed and retrieve data pertaining to an organisation’s human resources.”

The Saha and Majumder study (2017:85) outlined some objectives of using IT in performance appraisal as including the following; to help automate the processes of HRM and save time and cost and to reduce the efforts required and paper work involved. To help in the automation of performance appraisal organisations make use of various performance management software such as Workforce Performance Management and Talent Management Software which help to systematically record all data about employees performance,

store information in metrics where employees current performance can be compared with targets and standards, they also help to analyse the training needs of employees , monitor systematically employees progress and their review and feedback and the improvement in the performances.

HRM practitioners are also concerned with career planning for their organisations. According to Mamoudou and Joshi (2014:38), career planning tool is a generic, learning, knowledge-based system that helps top leaders to manage the personal development and path career of employees.

Mamoudou and Joshi (2014:34) point out that one of the most important online supports within Human Resources is tracking the Human Resources Development Core Processes.

HRIS Used In Human Resource Management Functions

A study by Adewoye and Obasan in Nigeria (2012:31) revealed the kind of HRIS used by some banks and the kind of HRM functions on which information technology is be employed. In their findings the indicate that many banks have gone beyond the traditional functions of HRM but have developed HRM Systems that support recruitment, selection, hiring, job placement, performance appraisals, employee benefit analysis, safety and security (Adewoye and Obasan, 2012:31). According to Adewoye and Obasan (2012:31) recent areas of HRIS implementation include: Payroll, Work time, Benefits administration, HR Information Management, Recruiting, Training/E-learning management systems and performance records. The findings of Adewoye and Obasan study (2012:33) indicated the following empirical evidences of the impact of IT on HRM.

Areas of impact of IT on HRM	Before adoption of IT	After adoption of IT
Efficiency of HRM activities and processes	49	85
Employee communication and engagement	49	79
Role and skills of HR managers	43	78
Overall average value in %	47	81

Source: Adewoye and Obasan (2012)
Source: Adewoye and Obasan (2012)

The findings showed an overall mean efficiency and effectiveness of HRM was 47 per cent before adoption of IT and later improved after adoption of IT by 34 percent to 81 per cent.

Objective Of This Study

The objective of this study was to assess the confidence of HRM Practitioners within some firms in the City of Blantyre in the efficiencies that HRIS bring into performance and the practice of HRM.

Methodology And Data Collection

To carry out this study, data were sourced from both primary and secondary sources. The secondary data sources were sourced through desktop research from different published materials, the internet and libraries while primary data were collected through semi-structured interviews with major players in HRM in some leading companies in the commercial City of Blantyre in Malawi. The questionnaire was designed based on four variables which were identified through literature review, these were: Efficiency of HRM activities and processes, Employee communication and engagement, Changing roles and Skills of HRM Practitioners and HRM position on a modern organisation's organisation chart.

Respondents were HRM Practitioners who have been in the industry for an average period of 10 to 15 years in the same company or not more than two companies during this period. The aim was to find out their experiences as Malawi adopted the digital aged from around the year 2000 to now. The dependent variables were selected in order to determine the role of information technology on the performance of human resource functions in the selected state-owned enterprises. Most companies in Malawi are smaller but the bigger ones are in the financial services sector and parastatals. The government sector has been very slow in adopting IT overall. 10 state-owned enterprises were purposively selected for the study. These state-owned enterprises have got national footprints across the three regions (provinces) of Malawi and hence have got not less than 200 employees on their payrolls at a minimum.

INDEPENDENT AND DEPENDENT VARIABLES

The independent variables were identified based on the core focus and skills of human resource management in the knowledge era among HRM Practitioners. The dependent variables were identified based on some ordinary human resource function tasks. The variables are as follows:

Independent Variables: Speed of Payroll processing and personnel records maintenance and retrieval

Dependent variables: Speed, efficiency, accuracy of information, timeliness and cost saving.

Independent variables: Changing role of human resource management function in the organisation and skills required for practitioners.

Dependent variables: Talent management, Employee training and development. IT skills, recruitment and placement.

Independent variables: Employee engagement, communication

Dependent variables: Performance appraisal, availability of information, work flexibility

Independent variable: Positioning of HMR Function in the organisation

Dependent variable: Strategic role of HRM, major function of the organisation, contributes to strategic decision making, ranks equally to other functions

The semi-structured interviews were conducted, questionnaires were filled by the interviewer and follow-up questions were put to the respondents based on their responses to the questions on the questionnaire. Summaries were made of all the responses recorded. Comparisons were made amongst the ten organisations of the role of information technology in the performance of these organisations before and after the introduction of HRIS. Data was then analysed for the study to demonstrate the role of information technology in the performance of HR functions in these organisations.

Themes and trends were noted from the summarised responses and determinations were made as to what the overall pictured was emerging from the results of the study. Thematic analysis was used to determine the overall themes emerging from the content of the results and from the ten state-owned enterprises some basic statistical analysis were made regarding the response rate and the similarity or differences in the results of the study.

Data Analysis And Findings Discussion

Role played by HRIS	Before (%)	After (%)
Speed of Payroll processing and personnel records maintenance and retrieval	40	90
Changing role of human resource management function in the organisation and skills required for practitioners and cost reduction	45	80
Employee engagement, communication, Job satisfaction	35	80
Positioning of HRM Function in the organisation	30	70
Overall average %	37.5	80

(Source: Primary data, 2020)

Descriptive statistics were used which considered overall total responses and percentages were calculated about the how each variable came out. The dependent variable were evaluated on the basis of the independent variables as discussed in the methodology of the study. Thematic analysis was carried out on the content as gathered from the respondents. Major themes such as efficiency, timeliness, less costly and non-traditional emerged from the data of the study.

The response mean for the role of IT on speed of payroll processing and personnel records maintenance and retrieval was 90% against 40% before the adoption of IT. The response mean for the role played by IT on the changing role of HRM and skill required for practitioners was 80% versus 40% for the period before the adoption of IT. The overall response average for the role played by IT on employee communication and engagement was 80% against 35% before adoption of IT. The response mean for the positioning

The table below shows the summarised responses for the time before and after HRIS were adopted by the companies: Tabulated evidence of the role of IT in performance of HRM Functions

It can be observed from the tabulated results that overall IT played a very big role in the improvement of the HRM functions. Before IT was adopted by these state-owned enterprises the overall effectiveness in the performance of HRM functions was at an average of 37.5 percent but after adopting IT performance improved to 80 percent an increased improvement of 42.5 percent. The speed of processing payroll and personnel records as well as their maintenance and retrieval was at 40% before IT was adopted but this improved to 90%. Salaries were processed on time; newly recruited employees were able to get their first pay in the month on employment or the next as opposed to the past when it could take between 3 months and 5 months before the newly employed could get their salaries. Employee records could take more than 5 months before they could be updated especially when someone has died or retired. Files kept manually could be lost between offices and accessing employee records improved with computerised information systems.

Human resource management was looked at as being about managing people who were not an important resource for the organisation, employee records and at times taking part in the recruitment of new employees. Other skills such as financial management were not considered to be part of it. With the adoption of IT all human resource managers had to be retrained in IT skills so that they could manage the payment of salaries a function which was in the hands of the account's office. With computerised payroll systems it meant that all salaries were to be prepared in the payroll office, which falls under HRM. New skills were learned and HR managers

replaced some personnel in the account's office. This led to streamlined and restructured accounts and human resources departments, fewer errors in salary calculations and payments. These effectively reduced some costs which were being incurred before IT was adopted.

Employee engagement, communication and job satisfaction through improved and timely information availability, work flexibility, enriched job descriptions, ability to apply for services online like leave taken, requests for salary advances, employee performance appraisals and overall top –bottom communication had the one of the lowest average score of 35% before adoption of IT improved to 80% after adoption of IT.

HRM function was considered as a supporting function to main organisational functions of Finance, Operations and General management (Administration). HR Managers were considered to mere pushers and custodians of files within the organisations and the score before adoption of IT was only 30%. The adoption of IT improved the rating to 70%. HRM was accorded a strategic role within the management structure of these organisations regarding talent identification and management and advising management about future needs of the organisation, which would require better skilled employees for the organisation.

CONCLUSION

The study has provided results that indicate the importance of adopting IT in the Malawian State-owned Enterprises. Four independent variables were identified. These were; Efficiency of HRM activities and processes, Employee communication and engagement, Changing roles and Skills of HRM Practitioners and HRM position on a modern organisation's organisation chart.

There was an overall improvement of 80% in the performance of HRM functions after the adoption of IT from an overall average of 37.5% before adoption. These state-owned enterprises only represented the rest.

Malawi has 60 state-owned entities and many public sector offices in urban and rural areas. Most of these do not have IT infrastructure in them, this means that the performance of HRM functions is still very poor. The government must move with speed to have them too adopt IT. The overall conclusion, however, is that IT has help to improve the performance of HRM functions in the state-owned enterprises and that assuming there has been doubts about its role, these should be erased and more should be done to fully have a digital public sector.

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